

Survival of *Ditylenchus angustus* in diseased stubble

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Rice disease Tiem Dot San caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* has occurred not only in deepwater rice in the Mekong Delta but also in double-transplanted rice of the main crop and in transplanted rice following the main crop.

Diseased rice hills with the panicle

still enclosed in the leaf sheath were collected (20-30 tillers/ hill) from an infested field and left on the surface of a grassy, nonflooded soil in late October 1976. Each week, three diseased plants were taken out randomly and the average percentage of surviving nematodes per plant was estimated by extracting the nematodes from each plant into 50 ml water in a petri dish and counting with a 1-ml counting slide.

The percentage of active nematodes decreased rapidly after harvest. After 3

weeks, the population was 40%. From 4 to 10 weeks the percentage was lower and stabilized as the nematodes adapted to dormant conditions. In early February 1977, no live nematodes were found.

The result shows the ability of *Ditylenchus angustus* to survive from the main rice crop to the crop transplanted in November and December and the need to find control measures against nematodes in crop residue. ■

Survival of sclerotia of rice stem rot fungus

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Sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae*, rice stem rot fungus, grown on sterilized rice culm pieces for 10 months were placed in soil layers 5, 15, and 25 cm deep in 5-cm-diameter polyethylene columns. The columns were buried in sandy clay loam (pH 7.3) with the top of the column at field level. Three water treatments were used: continuously dry; continuously wet to field capacity; and 3 days continuously wet, 10 days dry. Columns were removed at 4, 8, and 12 weeks and sclerotia retrieved by washing over an 80-mesh screen. Sclerotia viabil-

ity was tested by growing them on water agar containing penicillin and streptomycin sulfate at 3,000 ppm each (see figure).

Viability of sclerotia declined more in the surface soil. After 12 weeks, losses were 100% in dry soil, 91% in wet, and 84% in alternately wet and dry. At 15 and 25 cm depths, sclerotia viability was not much affected in wet and alternately wet and dry soil. In dry soil, viability was reduced to 30% at 15 cm depth and 0% at 25 cm. Pronounced loss in germinability of sclerotia in dry soil would suggest effects of desiccation, solar radiation, starvation, or other factors. ■

Viability of sclerotia of *Sclerotium oryzae* on paddy stubbles under dry or wet soil conditions.

Weed hosts of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Saw., a sheath rot pathogen of rice

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The host range of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Saw., the rice sheath rot pathogen, has not been widely studied. Because the disease often occurs in severe forms in almost all rice-growing areas of Kerala, irrespective of the cropping season, investigations on the source of inoculum are important. An initial survey at the Model Agronomic Research Station Farm, Karamana, Trivandrum district of Kerala, in fallow fields during the third crop season showed that two field weeds — *Cyperus difformis* L. and

Echinochloa crus-galli (L.) Beauv. were infected naturally with the rice sheath rot pathogen. The symptoms were identical to those on rice and pathogenicity tests of isolates from the weeds showed that they were highly pathogenic to rice.

Artificial inoculation tests at the College of Agriculture, Vellayani, screened out more weed hosts of the pathogen. Uninfected wetland field weeds were collected from different localities in the Trivandrum district and raised in earthen pots under controlled conditions. They were artificially inoculated with actively growing mycelial bits taken from a 10-day-old pure culture of the pathogen grown in potato dextrose agar. Mycelial bits of uniform size (5 mm) cut from the dish culture with a cork borer were introduced in the leaf

axils of test weeds. Inoculated plants were kept in above 92% humidity. Symptom development was recorded 5 to 8 days after inoculation.

Of the 10 weed plants tested, 5 — *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Monochoria vaginalis* (BURM. f.) Presl., *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus iria* L., and *Cyperus teneriffae* Poir — were recorded for the first time as pathogen hosts. ■

Control of helminthosporium leaf spot by foliar sprays

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The effect of chemicals on the control of helminthosporium leaf spot was studied